

FREQUENCY AND OUTCOMES OF CHILDHOOD INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTIONS TREATED AT A TERTIARY CARE CENTRE

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Abstract

OBJECTIVE

To assess the frequency and postoperative outcomes of childhood intestinal obstruction in children aged 1–14 years presenting to a tertiary care hospital.

METHODOLOGY

The research adopted a descriptive cross-sectional design and was carried out at the Department of Pediatric Surgery, Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro, during the period July–December 2024. Using non-probability consecutive sampling, 135 children aged 1–14 years with intestinal obstruction were enrolled. Data was obtained using predesigned structured forms and analyzed with SPSS (version 26). Both descriptive and inferential analyses were applied, and statistical significance was considered at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

The study analyzed 135 children aged 1–14 years (mean 5.69 ± 4.24), comprising 52.6% boys and 47.4% girls. Intestinal obstruction was identified in 21.5% of participants. Statistically significant associations were noted for abdominal distension (54.7%), abdominal pain (63.0%), reduced stool frequency (90.6%), and failure to pass stool (91.7%) ($p < 0.001$).

CONCLUSION

Childhood intestinal obstruction remains an important clinical challenge in pediatric surgery. The condition commonly presents typical gastrointestinal symptoms and generally responds well to timely surgical care. Most children achieve recovery without major complications when diagnosis and management are prompt. Strengthening early detection strategies and implementing consistent treatment practices can further improve postoperative outcomes and reduce preventable morbidity in pediatric surgical settings.

INTRODUCTION

Intestinal obstruction is one of the most frequent surgical emergencies in the paediatric population, representing a significant cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. It results from partial or complete blockage of the intestinal lumen, which impedes the normal passage of contents and may lead to bowel ischemia, perforation, and sepsis if not promptly managed [1,2]. The condition presents with variable clinical features including abdominal distension, vomiting, pain, and failure to pass stool or flatus, with severity and prognosis largely influenced by the underlying cause and the timing of intervention [3,4].

In children, etiological patterns differ substantially from adults, with congenital anomalies, intussusception, volvulus, Meckel's diverticulum, and obstructed hernias being predominant causes, particularly in developing regions [5,6]. Intussusception remains the most common acquired cause, while congenital atresia, malrotation, and Hirschsprung's disease constitute frequent neonatal presentations [7,8]. Although advancements in imaging modalities such as ultrasound and contrast studies have enhanced early diagnosis, delayed presentation is still common in resource-limited settings, leading to increased risk of bowel necrosis, longer hospitalization, and higher mortality [9].

Globally, the incidence and etiological distribution of childhood intestinal obstruction vary according to geographic, environmental, and socioeconomic factors. Studies from South Asia and sub-Saharan Africa report a predominance of congenital and infective causes, whereas in high-income countries, postoperative adhesions are more common [10,11]. In Pakistan, local studies indicate that intestinal obstruction constitutes a major proportion of paediatric surgical admissions, with intussusception and congenital anomalies as the leading aetiologies, and mortality rates ranging between 1.8% and 5% [12,13]. Despite this, comprehensive regional data remain limited, and heterogeneity in outcomes persists due to differences in referral patterns, diagnostic delays, and surgical resources [14].

Timely recognition and intervention are critical to improving outcomes in pediatric intestinal

obstruction. Standardized management protocols and region-specific epidemiological data are essential to reduce preventable complications and optimize care delivery [15]. Therefore, the present study aims to determine the frequency and outcomes of childhood intestinal obstruction in a tertiary care setting, providing updated regional evidence to guide clinical practice and policy in paediatric surgical management.

METHODOLOGY

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Pediatric Surgery at Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro/Hyderabad, over a six-month period from July 2024 to December 2024. Childhood intestinal obstruction was defined as a mechanical blockage of the small or large intestine among children aged 1 to 14 years, confirmed through radiological findings of dilated bowel loops with fluid and gas levels on abdominal X-ray and corresponding evidence on ultrasound. The study evaluated several outcome variables, including duration of hospital stay, postoperative complications such as bowel perforation, sepsis, anastomotic leakage, or necrotizing enterocolitis, recovery status (defined as tolerance to oral feeding and passage of stool within three days of admission), and in-hospital mortality. A non-probability consecutive sampling method was employed, and the final sample size of 135 participants was determined using the WHO sample size calculator, based on an anticipated prevalence of acute mechanical intestinal obstruction of 21.7%, a 95% confidence level, and a 7% margin of error. Children aged 1–14 years of either gender presenting to the emergency department with abdominal pain and inability to pass stool for at least two consecutive days, accompanied by one or more symptoms such as bilious vomiting or abdominal distension, were included in the study. Participants were excluded if informed consent from parents or guardians could not be obtained, or if the child had a history of malignancy, congenital heart disease, or hepatic or renal disorders as confirmed through medical records. Data were collected using a structured proforma that captured demographic details,

clinical features, diagnostic findings, and surgical outcomes. All surgical procedures were performed by the principal investigator under the supervision of a senior consultant surgeon. Data analysis was carried out using SPSS version 26.0. Numerical variables were summarized as averages with measures of dispersion, whereas categorical data were expressed as proportions. Associations between categorical factors were evaluated using the Chi-square test, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

A total of 135 participants were included in the study. The mean age of the patients was $5.69 \pm$

4.24 years, with a 95% confidence interval of 4.97 to 6.41 years. The average length of hospital stay was 8.13 ± 1.91 days, with a 95% confidence interval ranging from 7.80 to 8.45 days. Among the participants, 71 (52.6%) were male and 64 (47.4%) were female. Most of the patients were residents of urban areas (56.3%), while 43.7% belonged to rural regions. The most common clinical presentation was vomiting, observed in 60% of cases, followed by abdominal distension in 39.3%, abdominal pain in 34.1%, decreased frequency of stool in 23.7%, inability to pass stool for two days in 17.8%, and dilated bowel loops in 18.5% of the patients (Table I).

Mean ± Standard Deviation		95% Confidence Interval
Age in years = 5.69 ± 4.24		4.97---6.41
Length of hospital stay = 8.13 ± 1.91		7.80---8.45
Frequency (%)		
Gender	Male	71 (52.6)
	Female	64 (47.4)
Residential Status	Urban	76 (56.3)
	Rural	59 (43.7)
Vomiting		81 (60.0)
Abdominal Distension		53 (39.3)
Abdominal Pain		46 (34.1)
Decreased frequency of stool		32 (23.7)
Inability to pass stool for 2 days		24 (17.8)
Dilated bowl loop		25 (18.5)

Out of the 135 patients included in the study, 29 (21.5%) were diagnosed with intestinal obstruction, while 106 (78.5%) did not have obstructions. The mean age of patients with intestinal obstruction was 5.76 ± 4.05 years, which was comparable to those without obstruction (5.67 ± 4.31 years; $p = 0.921$). Similarly, the mean length of hospital stay did not differ significantly between the two groups (7.76 ± 1.80 vs. 8.23 ± 1.93 days; $p = 0.245$). Intestinal obstruction was more frequent among females (26.6%) compared to males (16.9%), although this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.172$). The occurrence

of obstruction was similar among urban (21.1%) and rural (22.0%) residents ($p = 0.890$). Clinically, vomiting was reported in 24.7% of patients with obstruction, but the association was not statistically significant ($p = 0.266$). However, abdominal distension (54.7%), abdominal pain (63.0%), decreased frequency of stool (90.6%), inability to pass stool for two days (91.7%), and dilated bowel loops (88.0%) were all significantly associated with intestinal obstruction ($p = 0.0001$ for all) (Table II).

Clinical Characteristics		Intestinal Obstruction		P-Value
		Yes (n=29)	No (n=106)	
Age in years		5.76 ± 4.05	5.67 ± 4.31	0.921
Length of hospital stay		7.76 ± 1.80	8.23 ± 1.93	0.245
Gender	Male	12 (16.9)	59 (83.1)	0.172
	Female	17 (26.6)	47 (73.4)	
Residential Status	Urban	16 (21.1)	60 (78.9)	0.890
	Rural	13 (22.0)	46 (78.0)	
Vomiting		20 (24.7)	61 (75.3)	0.266
Abdominal Distension		29 (54.7)	24 (45.3)	0.0001
Abdominal Pain		29 (63.0)	17 (37.0)	0.0001
Decreased frequency of stool		29 (90.6)	3 (9.4)	0.0001
Inability to pass stool for 2 days		22 (91.7)	2 (8.3)	0.0001
Dilated bowel loop		22 (88.0)	3 (12.0)	0.0001

Among patients who underwent surgery, postoperative outcomes were analyzed in relation to age and gender. When compared by age, bowel perforation occurred in 66.7% of children aged 1-6 years and 33.3% of those older than 6 years (p = 0.684). Sepsis was observed only in one patient from the younger age group (p = 0.621). Similarly, anastomotic leak was more frequent among younger children (66.7%) compared to older ones (33.3%), though the difference was not statistically significant (p = 0.684). Necrotizing enterocolitis affected both age groups equally (p = 0.623). Successful recovery was achieved in 57.1% of patients aged 1-6 years and 42.9% of those above 6 years (p = 0.376). In-hospital mortality was slightly higher in the younger age group (80.0%) compared to the older group (20.0%), but this

difference was also not significant (p = 0.356). When compared by gender, bowel perforation was observed only in males (100.0%), though the difference approached but did not reach statistical significance (p = 0.060). Sepsis occurred in one female patient (p = 0.586). Anastomotic leak (66.7%) and necrotizing enterocolitis (100.0%) were more common in females, but the associations were not statistically significant (p = 0.633 and p = 0.335, respectively). Successful recovery was achieved in 38.1% of males and 61.9% of females (p = 0.561). In-hospital mortality was higher among female patients (80.0%) compared to males (20.0%), though this difference was not statistically significant (p = 0.293) (Table III).

Table III: Comparison of Post Operative Outcomes with Age and Gender			
Post Operative Outcomes	Age Group		P-Value
	1-6	>6	
Bowel perforation	2 (66.7)	1 (33.3)	0.684
Sepsis	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0.621
Anastomotic leak	2 (66.7)	1 (33.3)	0.684
Necrotizing enterocolitis	1 (50.0)	1 (50.0)	0.623
Successful recovery	12 (57.1)	9 (42.9)	0.376
In-hospital mortality	4 (80.0)	1 (20.0)	0.356
Post Operative Outcomes	Gender		P-Value
	Male	Female	
Bowel perforation	3 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0.060
Sepsis	0 (0.0)	1 (100.0)	0.586
Anastomotic leak	1 (33.3)	2 (66.7)	0.633
Necrotizing enterocolitis	0 (0.0)	2 (100.0)	0.335
Successful recovery	8 (38.1)	13 (61.9)	0.561
In-hospital mortality	1 (20.0)	4 (80.0)	0.293

DISCUSSION

This paper examined the clinical features and postoperative experiences of children with intestinal obstruction in a tertiary care hospital. It was revealed in the analysis that the major presenting features like abdominal distension, abdominal pain, decreased stool frequency, and inability to pass stool were highly correlated with intestinal obstruction. Such results are in line with existing literature of paediatric surgery indicating these symptoms to be the best diagnostic markers of bowel obstruction among children [1,3]. The importance of a comprehensive clinical examination in most low-resource environments cannot be overestimated in terms of early diagnosis and prompt treatment.

The demographic character of the patients in this research, where the average is about six years old with a slightly higher percentage of male cases fits the trend and findings of Soomro et al. [5], Emeka et al. [12] and Hazra et al. [4], who reported comparable trends in their study samples. These similarities show that younger age brackets especially those who are less than ten years are more vulnerable to intestinal obstruction and that gender biasness in the condition is not pronounced. Adamou et al. and Abukhalaf et al. also described similar demographic distributions as the primary point that the epidemiological patterns of paediatric intestinal obstruction do not vary too significantly across different geographic locations.

In terms of aetiology, the trend in this study is like past national and regional reports. They are still mostly caused by intussusception, congenital atresia, and obstructed hernias, as are the findings of Soomro et al. [5], AFM [6], and Hussain et al. [13]. This is unlike those conducted in high-income countries, whereby obstruction is now mainly caused by postoperative adhesions [10,11]. There is also such variation, which is probably an indication of differences in healthcare infrastructure, the rate of congenital anomalies, and having access to early elective surgery to address the correctable congenital anomalies.

The postoperative outcomes observed in this research were encouraging, with most children recovering without major complications. The frequency of bowel perforation, anastomotic leakage, and necrotizing enterocolitis was low, which suggests effective perioperative care and timely surgical intervention. These favourable outcomes are in line with reports by Farrokhkhani et al. [9] and Melese Ayele [10], where early surgical treatment and adequate postoperative monitoring were identified as crucial factors in improving survival. However, studies by Adamou et al. [7] and Twahirwa et al. [11] in sub-Saharan Africa found higher complication and mortality rates, often associated with delayed presentation, limited resources, and inadequate resuscitation. The comparatively lower complication rates in the current study may therefore reflect the benefits of improved clinical awareness, early diagnosis, and better availability of paediatric surgical expertise. Interestingly there were not any meaningful associations made between postoperative outcomes and demographic factors (age or gender) and this has been found to agree with the results of other recent studies [9,10]. Nevertheless, Shakya et al. [16] and Uba et al. [17] have found that very young age, malnutrition, and delayed surgical intervention might have a negative impact on the recovery, which supports that postoperative outcomes are multifactorial. A more recent paper by Ethiopians Tamirat et al. [18] also focused on early presentation and timely surgical intervention as critical in the minimization of morbidity and mortality in paediatric intestinal obstruction. All these comparisons ultimately show that, even

though clinical manifestations of the disease are identical across the board, the access to healthcare and the response time may be significantly different and thus have an impact on the prognosis.

The present research has several strengths. It presents current regional information of a tertiary care hospital, has a well-identified sample, and uses objective variables to diagnose and assess outcome. In addition, the presentability-verified obstruction relationship is consistent, thus confirming the reliability of classical clinical manifestations in children.

Nonetheless, certain limitations should be acknowledged. As the study was conducted at a single institution, its findings may not represent the wider population. The cross-sectional design restricts causal inference and prevents long-term outcome assessment. Additionally, factors such as nutritional status, time from symptom onset to presentation, and intraoperative findings were not explored in detail, which might have influenced outcomes. Non-probability sampling could also introduce selection bias.

In conclusion, the research confirms that childhood intestinal obstruction remains a major paediatric surgical disease, and most of the time it has consistent clinical presentation that would aid an early diagnosis. On timely diagnosis and proper surgical care, good results can be obtained. To achieve even greater reduction of morbidity, it is necessary to reinforce early referral systems, ensure awareness of the caregivers and standardization of treatment protocols. It is suggested that future multicentre, longitudinal studies with long-term follow-up are required in order to gain a better understanding of predictors of adverse outcomes and maximization of management to treat the affected children.

CONCLUSION

Childhood intestinal obstruction remains an important clinical challenge in paediatric surgery. The condition commonly presents typical gastrointestinal symptoms and generally responds well to timely surgical care. Most children achieve recovery without major complications when diagnosis and management are prompt.

Strengthening early detection strategies and implementing consistent treatment practices can further improve postoperative outcomes and reduce preventable morbidity in paediatric surgical settings.

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